

D6.4.4.1

Streamlining Long-Term Energy System Scenario Data Annotation

Streamlining Long-Term Energy System Scenario Annotation: Using the NFDI4Energy Annotator with the Open Energy Ontology

Finn Niklas Peters (<https://orcid.org/0009-0003-3172-997X>)¹

Aamir Muhammad (<https://orcid.org/0009-0002-9374-1029>)²

Felix Engel (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3060-7052>)²

Mirko Schäfer (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8029-949X>)¹

Mirjam Stappel (<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3722-5564>)³

¹ University of Freiburg, INATECH, <https://ror.org/0245cg223>, Emmy-Noether-Str. 2, 79110 Freiburg

² TIB Leibniz Information Centre for Science and Technology, <https://ror.org/04aj4c181>, Welfengart 1 B, 30167 Hannover

³ Osnabrück University, <https://ror.org/04qmmjx98>, Neuer Graben 29 / Schloss, 49074 Osnabrück

Published by

University of Freiburg

Acknowledgements

The authors of this article have used various preparatory works from the NFDI4Energy to create this portrait, and references have been made where possible. Thanks to all those who are not named.

The authors would like to thank the German Federal Government, the German State Governments, and the Joint Science Conference (GWK) for their funding and support as part of the NFDI4Energy consortium. The work was funded by the German Research Foundation (DFG) – 501865131 within the German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI, www.nfdi.de).

License

This document is published under the [Attribution 4.0 International \(CC BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/). This license allows users to distribute, remix, adapt, and build upon the material in any medium or format, so long as attribution is given to the creator.

The license allows for commercial use.

Table of Contents

General Information.....	3
Summary	3
Deliverable within NFDI4Energy.....	3
Deliverable	4

General Information

Summary

The comparison of long-term energy scenarios faces significant challenges. Even if scenario data is publicly available with an open license, it is often presented in different formats with the variables lacking semantic standardization due to differing naming conventions and model structures. This makes aligning variables that represent the same concept a difficult, time-consuming, and manual process. This showcase addresses these challenges by applying NFDI4Energy services. We demonstrate a workflow using the NFDI4Energy Annotator to generate initial mappings of scenario variables to the Open Energy Ontology (OEO) and apply it to scenario data in the IAMC format from the Ariadne project. While these suggestions require manual review, the process significantly reduces the manual workload and provides a structured pathway for annotating scenario datasets using the Open Energy Ontology.

Deliverable within NFDI4Energy

The [TIB Terminology Service](#) with the [NFDI4Energy Annotator](#) and the [Open Energy Ontology \(OEO\)](#) are all resources maintained and partly developed as part of TA4 in NFDI4Energy. These tools were utilized in this showcase, and suggestions for improvement collected based on this application.

Deliverable (Showcase description)

Internal Documentation

Title: Streamlining Long-Term Energy System Scenario Data Annotation: Using the NFDI4Energy Annotator with the Open Energy Ontology

Authors: Finn Niklas Peters, Aamir Muhammad, Felix Engel, Mirko Schäfer, Mirjam Stappel

Contact person: Mirko Schäfer, mirko.schaefer@inatech.uni-freiburg.de

Date: 01/2026

Abstract:

Comparing energy system models (ESOMs) is essential for identifying robust policy pathways, yet inconsistent naming conventions often make cross-study analysis labor-intensive. To address this, we applied a streamlined workflow using the NFDI4Energy ecosystem to semantically annotate scenario data. By mapping IAMC variables to the [Open Energy Ontology \(OEO\)](#), we transform fragmented datasets into machine-readable formats. Our showcase utilizes the [NFDI4Energy Annotator](#) to automate term suggestions, significantly reducing manual workload while maintaining accuracy through targeted expert review with the help of [TIB Terminology Service](#). This methodology enhances data interoperability and enables automated SPARQL queries, contributing to making energy research more transparent, reproducible, and accessible for future policy design.

Links:

- [Matching Proposals for IAMC Format Terms for OEO](#)

NFDI4Energy input:

- [Open Energy Ontology \(OEO\)](#)
- [TIB Terminology Service](#)
- [NFDI4Energy Annotator](#)

TAs involved:

TA4, TA6

Energy research:

Long-term energy scenarios, often created with Energy System Optimization Models (ESOMs), provide detailed insights into possible design options for and pathways towards future energy systems. Comparing these scenarios is essential to identify commonalities and differences across various models and studies. However, such comparisons are notoriously challenging. Studies use different variable naming conventions and model structures, making it difficult to align variables that ultimately represent the same concept. This alignment process often requires significant manual effort.

Motivation:

Our motivation is to streamline and simplify the creation of inter-scenario and inter-model comparisons. To achieve this, ontologically annotated scenario datasets are required. Using a standardized vocabulary like the Open Energy Ontology (OEO) allows for a consistent and machine-

readable mapping between variables across different studies. However, this process depends on active community participation in annotating datasets with relevant ontological terms. This step is often a bottleneck, as it can be time-consuming and requires specialized knowledge of ontologies like the OEO. For this showcase, we used several services from the NFDI4Energy ecosystem, including the OEO, the TIB Terminology Service, and the NFDI4Energy Annotator to annotate an extensive scenario dataset from the Ariadne project.

Enhancement:

We applied multiple tools and services to annotate a large scenario dataset, which uses three models: REMod, REMIND, and PyPSA-DE. The dataset follows the IAMC format, and the main challenge was to map its variables to the Open Energy Ontology (OEO), thus enabling machine readability and searchability via SPARQL queries in the envisaged model comparison functionality.

To simplify this task, we first used the NFDI4Energy Annotator tool to generate suggestions for IAMC variable terms through its REST API and semantic annotation capabilities. While these automated annotations are not perfect and still require human review, they significantly reduce the manual workload and provide an accessible entry point for first-time users.

Next, we manually reviewed the suggested terms to ensure semantic accuracy. When discrepancies were found, we used the TIB Terminology Service to search for more appropriate concepts. If no adequate term existed, we proposed enhancements to the OEO to improve its coverage and precision.

The showcase thus contributes to different goals:

- It prepares a large and relevant dataset from the landscape of German energy system scenario to be included in the scenario comparison workflow developed in NFDI4Energy.
- By annotating this large dataset using the IAMC format, the integration of further scenarios using this format is facilitated (several European projects or scenarios entering the IPCC Assessment Reports use this format).
- Gaps in the Open Energy Ontology are identified and possible extensions discussed.
- The documentation of the annotation process supports other researchers when annotating scenario data using this workflow.

Potential testimonials: /

Lessons learned:

Some pitfalls were identified, offering insights for improving both workflow and tool quality.

- In some cases, alternative terms for the respective OEO concepts were missing and we created issues to add them, so the annotator tool would have a better proposition.
- Many terms did not have a precise match in the OEO. Therefore, we concluded that an extension with these terms is necessary and discussed it in the OEO developer meeting.
- While some terms were missing, there were also too many terms in the OEO which made it difficult to find appropriate terms. Thus, we decided to create a new ontology, the “Long Term Energy Scenario Ontology (LESO)” that uses a subset of the OEO as a core and adds other terms that are required for the appropriate presentation of scenarios.
- The annotator tool only searched through the classes, but not the individuals, which is a problem when it comes to emission sectors since they are all defined as individuals, but play an integral role in the depiction of long-term scenario data.

Brief sections for the website

The Showcase's Starting Point in Energy System Research

Long-term energy scenarios based on Energy System Optimization Models (ESOMs) provide detailed insights into possible pathways for Germany's future energy system. A comparison across different models and studies supports better policy design and research transparency. However, such comparisons are challenging. Different studies use different variable naming conventions and model structures. This makes it difficult to align variables that represent the same concept—a process that often requires significant manual effort and hinders data interoperability.

Motivation and Research Requirements

Ontologically annotated datasets facilitate simpler and more automated scenario comparisons. Using a shared vocabulary like the Open Energy Ontology (OEO) allows for a consistent, machine-readable mapping of variables across different studies. However, this annotation process is time-consuming and requires specialized knowledge of ontologies. Our goal was to address this challenge by using NFDI4Energy services to make semantic annotation more efficient, reproducible, and interoperable.

NFDI4Energy Solution

We demonstrated a workflow for annotating large scenario datasets (using the IAMC format) by applying a combination of NFDI4Energy services and resources:

- **Open Energy Ontology (OEO)**
- **TIB Terminology Service**
- **NFDI4Energy Annotator**

The main challenge was to map scenario variables to the **OEO**, making them machine-readable and searchable via **SPARQL queries** for automated comparison.

Our process used the **NFDI4Energy Annotator tool** to automatically generate annotation suggestions. While these **require human review**, they **significantly reduce the manual workload**. We then used the **TIB Terminology Service** for manual review and proposed **enhancements to the OEO** when gaps were found.

This showcase prepares a large dataset for scenario comparison, helps facilitate the integration of other IAMC-format data, and provides documentation to support other researchers in their own annotation workflows.